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Effects of rear cavities on the wake behind an accelerating D-shaped bluff body

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We investigate experimental and numerically the transient development of the wake induced by a constant acceleration of a D-shaped bluff body starting from rest and reaching a permanent regime of Reynolds number $Re = 2000$, under different values of acceleration and implementing three distinct rear geometrical configurations. Thus, alongside the classical blunt base, two control passive devices, namely a straight cavity and an optimized, curved cavity, recently designed using adjoint optimization techniques, have been also used to assess their performance in transient flow conditions. Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) measurements were performed in a towing tank to characterize the near wake development in the early transient stages. It has been observed that the flow first develops symmetric shear layers with primary eddies attracted towards the base of the body due to the flow suction generated by the accelerated motion. Eventually, the interaction between the upper and lower shear layers provokes the destabilization of the flow and the rupture of symmetry of the wake, finally giving rise to an alternate transitional vortex shedding regime. The transition between these phases is sped-up when the optimized cavity is used, reaching earlier the permanent flow conditions. In particular, the use of the optimized geometry has been shown to limit the growth of the primary eddies, decreasing both the recirculation and vortex formation length and providing with a more regularized, less chaotic transient alternate shedding process. In addition, numerical simulations (DNS) have been performed to evaluate the distribution of forces induced by the addition of rear cavities. In general, the aforementioned smoother and faster transition related to the use of optimized cavity, translates into a lower averaged value of the drag coefficient, together with less energetic instantaneous force fluctuations, independently of the acceleration value.

I. INTRODUCTION

The flow around bluff bodies constitutes a relevant problem in aerodynamics, due to its importance in many industrial applications, such as transport industry. In particular, wakes behind trucks or heavy vehicles are characterized by a massive detachment of flow behind them, which generates large values of the drag and oscillating forces on the body¹. These aerodynamic forces have a significant impact on the fuel consumption, and therefore, on the emission of greenhouse effect gases. In that regard, Bradley² estimated that at least a 20% of trailer's fuel consumption (driving at 105 km/h), is related to aerodynamic losses, i.e. drag. More precisely, an approximate 25% of such drag resistance corresponds to the rear part of these types of vehicles³. Consequently, a large effort has been devoted during the past years to develop flow control and drag reduction strategies, acting on the rear part of bluff bodies, mostly using different simplified models which retain the main wake features of heavy vehicles⁴⁻⁸. Regardless of the nature of the control, these strategies usually act modifying the near wake or the boundary layer detachment, using among others: blowing⁹, rear cavities^{10,11} or flaps¹². The design of most of such techniques is based on the profound knowledge of the flow features, although the recent application of sensitivity maps^{13,14}, in combination with optimization algorithms¹⁵, may provide with more efficient control devices. Using these approaches, Lorite-Díez *et al.*¹⁶ have proposed an improved curved, optimized rear cavity, implemented in a D-shaped body, similar to that in Pastoor *et al.*⁶, which is capable of providing with a total drag reduction greater than 25% with respect to the body without cavity.

Traditionally, these studies on drag reduction and wake control are focused on permanent flow regimes, leaving aside the analysis of the performance of such strategies under transient conditions, which are very common in aerodynamics applications, such as vehicles accelerating or overtaking maneuvers¹⁷.

Therefore, it seems natural to extend the aforementioned studies on flow control to more complex, transient flow phenomena. In that sense, several previous works have characterized the flow regimes and force distributions emerging from impulsive dynamics of simplified bluff bodies. For instance, Odar and Hamilton¹⁸ proposed an analytical equation to model the force on an accelerating sphere, and subsequently validated it through towing tank tests, accounting for the velocity and the acceleration of the sphere as well as time history terms. Later on, Roos and Willmarth¹⁹ evaluated experimentally the recirculation bubble behind a sphere and a disk, along with the transient

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forces and moments acting on them, varying the acceleration for Reynolds numbers in the range $5 \leq \text{Re} \leq 100000$. These investigations were subsequently extended to cylinders and prisms by several authors, both numerical and experimentally^{20–24}. More recently, Tonui and Summer²⁵ experimentally investigated the effect of prismatic geometries on the near wake topology, using a towing tank and particle image velocimetry (PIV) measurements, focusing on the recirculation length and strength of the vortices shed. In addition, the works by Fernando *et al.*^{26,27}, have assessed the separation mechanism, forces and vortex evolution in the wake of accelerating spheres and plates, using a similar experimental set-up. In general, during the body's accelerating period, the drag force is mainly governed by the added mass term. Next, there is a transient period toward the permanent vortex shedding regime, where large amplitude drag variations occur stemming from the evolution of the near wake, which finally lead to the typical alternate shedding at a characteristic natural frequency.

These aforementioned force distributions are strongly linked to near wake transient initial development. Furthermore, it has been also proven that such stages and flow features, are highly dependent on the geometry of the bluff body²⁵. Consequently, if the performance of any passive control device is to be evaluated in transient flows, a profound characterization of flow dynamics is needed. Within this frame, we study three different rear geometries (i.e. blunt base, straight cavity and curved, optimized cavity) implemented in a D-shaped body, which is accelerated from rest, to evaluate their efficiency in terms of drag reduction and wake instability in transient conditions. Following the aforementioned premises, we perform herein experimental and numerical analyses of the transient dynamics, to study flow detachment, vortex formation and shedding, and forces time evolution, for four different acceleration values and a Reynolds number of $\text{Re} = 2000$. These results complement those by Lorite-Díez *et al.*¹⁶ in permanent flow regime, with the aim at looking for the most efficient overall control alternative.

Thus, the experimental set-up and numerical techniques employed are first described in Section II. Section III is devoted to the experimental results, obtained in a towing tank, that have allowed the characterization of the early stages of wake development. Next, Section IV presents a comparison of the experimental measurements with the results obtained from direct numerical simulations, to subsequently perform a numerical study on the forces distributions and drag reduction. Finally, the main conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ASPECTS

A. Problem description

We study the three-dimensional flow around a D-shaped body of semi-ellipsoidal nose, as in Lorite-Díez *et al.*¹⁶ (see Fig. 1a), of an incompressible fluid of density ρ and viscosity μ . The body of height $H = 4$ cm, length $L = 3.83H$ and spanwise width $W = 7.64H$, implements three different rear geometries: a blunt base without cavity (WOC), a straight cavity (STR) and a curved, optimized cavity (OPT) (see Fig. 1c). The cavities feature a depth of $0.3H$ and a wall thickness of $0.05H$, while the distance between outer edges for the curved cavity is $h = 0.853H$. The origin of the coordinate system, (x, y, z) , is placed at the base of the cavity, and at half of the spanwise and transversal lengths. Note that in the case of the body without cavity, the body base is at $x = 0.3H$. The body is impulsively started from rest, at a constant acceleration, a , reaching a final permanent regime with a constant velocity, $u_{max} = 5$ cm/s (see inset in Fig. 1a). The aforementioned overall dimensions ensure a quasi two-dimensional flow, being therefore the side edge effects negligible in the near wake and force distributions, except for a very small lateral spanwise region. Under the previous conditions, the characteristic scales for length, velocity, acceleration, pressure, and time, are respectively: H , u_{max} , u_{max}^2/H , ρu_{max}^2 and H/u_{max} . In all, four different dimensionless accelerations, $a^* = aH/u_{max}^2$, have been considered for the analysis, namely $a^* = 0.08, 0.2, 0.5$ and 1 . Besides, a non-dimensional displacement parameter is defined to quantify the downstream physical distance traveled by the body, Δx , as $s^* = \Delta x/H$. Finally, the permanent regime is characterized by the Reynolds number, $\text{Re} = \rho u_{max}H/\mu = 2000$. The experimental facility used, as well as the numerical model implemented, are next described.

B. Experimental set-up

The experiments were carried out in a towing tank of $2 \text{ m} \times 0.6 \text{ m} \times 0.6 \text{ m}$, which allows optical access from all sides. The body is towed and controlled through an Adjustable Frequency Drive (AFD), iG5A series, connected to an AC motor that provides a stable linear displacement for velocities up to 0.66 m/s. AFD allows to precisely control the velocity and acceleration, with sensitivities of $70 \mu\text{m/s}$ and $80 \mu\text{m/s}^2$ respectively.

The body, manufactured using a 3D, selective laser sintering (SLS) printer, was vertically immersed in the water tank as shown in Fig. 1(b), and aligned with respect to the towing direction by means of a 3-Axis stage with micrometric adjustment. In addition, a thin plate, placed at the free surface, was used to remove any perturbation introduced

Figure 1. (a) Problem configuration and numerical domain, (b) experimental set-up and (c) rear geometries investigated. Insets in (a) and (b) show the time varying inlet velocity $u_\infty(t)$.

82 by the free surface waves produced during the experimental measurements. The separation between the body and
 83 bottom of the tank was less than $H/2$ in order to avoid edge effects.

84 Wake measurements were carried out using time resolved, planar particle image velocimetry (PIV). To that aim,
 85 a 5 W, Diode-Pumped Solid State (DPSS) green laser was used to create a sheet, which was positioned horizontally
 86 normal to z -axis of the body and centered with respect to y -axis. The flow was seeded with $10 \mu\text{m}$, neutrally-buoyant
 87 hollow glass spheres and a CCD-sensor, High-Speed Camera, towed alongside the body, was used to record images
 88 at a rate of 125 fps, with a resolution of 1024×512 pixels. This set-up provided with an approximate Field of View
 89 (FoV) of $4H \times 2H$ behind the body at midspan of water depth, which allowed to properly capture the recirculation
 90 region and vortex shedding. The exposure was accordingly adjusted to obtain static particles between consecutive
 91 snapshots.

92 Series of around 2000 pair of images were processed in each experimental case, using the Matlab®toolbox PIVlab²⁸,
 93 applying a pre-processing of images with interrogation windows size of 16×16 pixels with 50% overlapping area, what
 94 results into a vector field of 124×62 and a spatial resolution of $0.034H$. The associated uncertainty was estimated
 95 to be $\pm 5\%$.

96 C. Numerical details

97 Additionally, direct numerical simulations (DNS) were performed to complement and extend the experimental
 98 measurements, for the same flow conditions. To that end, the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations were solved
 99 numerically using the finite volume toolbox OpenFoam®, within a prismatic domain (see Fig. 1a), extending in the
 100 axial x -coordinate $21H$ downstream of the body rear edges, $7.85H$ upstream of the body nose, and spanning $21H$
 101 in the transversal y -coordinate, and $7.64H$ in the spanwise z -coordinate. Appropriate boundary conditions were
 102 imposed, namely no-slip condition at the body wall, Σ_w , slip conditions at the domain sides, Σ_s , and an outflow
 103 condition for the outer boundary, Σ_o . At the inlet, we imposed a prescribed time varying velocity field normal to the
 104 boundary Σ_i , i.e. $(u_x, u_y, u_z) = (u_\infty^*, 0, 0)$, where the dimensionless input velocity, $u_\infty^*(t^*)$, follows,

$$u_\infty^*(t^*) = \begin{cases} a^* t^* & t^* \leq 1/a^*, \\ 1 & t^* > 1/a^*. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

105 The equations were discretized using Gauss linear second-order schemes for the spatial terms of the Navier-Stokes
 106 equations, a Crank-Nicholson scheme for the temporal integration, whereas the pressure-velocity coupling was solved
 107 by means of a Pressure-Implicit Split-Operator (PISO) algorithm²⁹. A grid sensitivity study was conducted as in
 108 Lorite-Díez *et al.*¹⁶ to guarantee that the results did not depend on the mesh used. As an outcome, a mesh of nearly
 109 3×10^6 cells was selected, which concentrates nodes close to the body wall and cavity edges, where larger physical
 110 gradients are present. Finally, the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number was limited to a maximum value of 0.5, to
 111 guarantee computational stability. On the other hand, in the remaining, non-dimensional variables will be used, with
 112 the asterisk dropped to simplify the notation, unless otherwise stated.

Figure 2. Time sequence of spanwise vorticity ω_z of the near wake, obtained by PIV measurements, for the optimized cavity at $Re = 2000$ and $a = 0.5$. Contours of vorticity range $\omega_z \in [-8, 8]$. Here the negative vorticity contours are in red and the positive ones in blue.

113 III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS: EARLY STAGES WAKE CHARACTERIZATION

114 This section presents experimental results which describe the main flow characteristics, for the three rear geometries under study, and the different selected accelerations. Thus, we first describe the wake development obtained
 115 experimentally, to subsequently characterize the recirculation region and vortex downstream evolution.
 116

117 A. Experimental flow description

118 As mentioned in Section II, wake measurements were performed using PIV technique, which provided with a detailed
 119 description of the wake regimes and vortex development for the three base geometries under study, allowing to identify
 120 the main differences exhibited in terms of transient flow events. To that end, we will describe the main flow features
 121 using time sequences of the spanwise vorticity, ω_z , where

$$\omega_z = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y}, \quad (2)$$

122 to analyse the role of different geometries and acceleration values.

123 Fig. 2 shows the initial stages of the flow for the optimized cavity (OPT) and an intermediate value of acceleration,
 124 $a = 0.5$. In addition to provide the dimensionless time, t , we have included the value of the distance traveled by the
 125 body, s , given by,

$$s(t) = \begin{cases} at^2/2 & t \leq 1/a, \\ t - 1/2a & t > 1/a. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

126 The body starts from rest at $t = 0$, within a quiescent flow (Fig. 2a), and during and shortly after the impulsive
 127 motion (notice that at $t = 2$ the body's motion reaches the permanent velocity regime), the flow separates at the
 128 rear cavity edges, and the shear layer rolls up forming two symmetric counter-rotating eddies, which grow with time
 129 (Figs. 2b-c). As it will be shown later in Section IV, the inertial motion generates a low pressure near the base of
 130 the body that, together with the strong circulation of eddies, drives them towards the cavity, while preserving a quasi
 131 symmetric wake configuration (Fig. 2d). These primary vortices grow inside the cavity (Fig. 2e), whose size precludes
 132 them from further growing, making the flow separate downstream from the body base (Figs. 2f-g). In particular,
 133 Fig. 2(g) shows that, for the case at hand, the primary eddy with negative, clockwise vorticity remains inside the
 134 cavity, while the positive, counterclockwise one is ejected. Simultaneously, due to the unstable nature of the flow
 135 at $Re = 2000$, the symmetry is broken and the interaction between upper and lower shear layers triggers a vortex
 136 shedding process (Figs. 2g-j), which eventually will lead to the characteristic alternate vortex shedding in permanent
 137 regime (note that for $t = 7$, a negative small vortex is being already convected downstream, while a positive one starts
 138 to detach). At the same time, the former primary eddy, which was trapped inside the cavity, progressively dissipates
 139 giving rise to an irrotational region inside the cavity, as Fig. 2(j) suggests. For the sake of a clearer interpretation of
 140 the results, three different phases can be defined during the transient process, namely: *phase A* or initial symmetric
 141 wake development (Figs. 2a-d); *phase B* characterized by the vortices interaction and symmetry breaking without
 142 shedding (Figs. 2e-f); and *phase C* in which the shedding process begins (Figs. 2g-j).

143 The described dynamics is highly related to the distribution of forces acting on the body, as it will be shown later in
 144 the discussion of the numerical results (see Sect. IV). Therefore, a noticeable modification of the drag value might be
 145 obtained if important flow topology changes are introduced during the early transient stages, for instance, by means
 146 of actuating on the vortex formation distance or limiting the size of eddies.

147 In this regard, to evaluate the effect of geometry, Fig. 3 shows the near wake evolution, characterized through
 148 vorticity contours, for the three rear configurations considered herein, namely, the blunt-based body, and the bodies
 149 implementing straight and optimized cavities, respectively, for the largest value of acceleration $a = 1$. At initial
 150 stages ($t < 4$), a symmetric wake development takes place for all geometries, although the shear layer and vortex
 151 topologies are different. In the case of the blunt-based body (left column, Fig. 3), primary eddies are located very
 152 close to the base, whereas for the bodies with cavities, the formation takes place outside the cavity (see middle and
 153 right columns). Besides, while the straight cavity leads to shear layers which are initially aligned with the cavity
 154 blades, in the case of the optimized cavity, the curved geometry induces an inward transversal flow, which makes the
 155 shear layers fold towards the axis, decreasing the distance between the cores of both vortices. At $t = 4$, the primary
 156 vortices move towards the body base in the case without a cavity and get inside the cavity in the bodies with a
 157 straight and a curved cavities. However, whereas for the two first configurations (blunt base and straight cavity) the
 158 wake remains symmetric, i.e. *phase A* has not been yet completed, the wake behind the optimized cavity body is
 159 already asymmetric, indicating that *phase B* has already started. Physically, the wake behind the blunt-based body
 160 is aligned with the streamwise direction, but the absence of any transversal barrier does not limit the growth of the
 161 eddies, curving the shear layers in the vicinity of the rear edges, while preserving its symmetry (see $t = 6$, *phase A*).
 162 Conversely, for the bodies with cavities the growth of eddies is transversally restricted by the cavity, which accelerates
 163 the asymmetry of the wake and elongates the primary vortices. The latter is concomitant with the formation of
 164 auto-induced shear layers of opposite signs in the vicinity of the flow detachment (as it can be seen for the straight
 165 cavity at $t = 6$). In the particular case of the optimized cavity, the closer and more intricate interaction between
 166 vortices, together with the larger space restriction, triggers earlier the shear layer oscillations and symmetry breaking,
 167 characterizing the transition to *phase B* (at $t = 4$), and the subsequent non-regular vortex shedding inception defining
 168 *phase C* (for $t \geq 6$). Similarly, for the straight cavity, the *phase B* does not take place until $t = 6$ and vortex shedding
 169 is first discernible for $t = 8$, whereas the *phase B*, symmetry breaking scenario appears for $t \geq 8$ for the blunt-based
 170 body. Interestingly, at the last stages of the described early transients, a nearly irrotational region forms at the
 171 body base (especially noticeable for the blunt base case) which stems from the flow deceleration that occurs after the
 172 steady motion of the body is set ($t > 1$). This deceleration translates into a local pressure increase that promotes
 173 the downstream convection of eddies, which coexist with the dissipation of vortices trapped inside this region. This
 174 phenomenon gives rise to an unsteady flow regime characterized by the alternate, non-regularized shedding of vorticity,
 175 which is accompanied by the lengthening of the near wake and recirculation bubble (as it will be shown below), and
 176 that eventually will conclude with the characteristic regular permanent flow regime at a constant Re . Finally, notice
 177 that this process is weaker for the optimized geometry, as Fig. 3 shows, which clearly provokes a faster transition
 178 towards the mentioned non-regular shedding. Consequently, different behaviors of drag time sequences are expected
 180 for these three geometries.

181 Similar flow features can be observed for lower values of acceleration, a . In that sense, Fig. 4 depicts time sequence

Figure 3. Time sequence of spanwise vorticity ω_z of the near wake, obtained by PIV measurements, for the blunt-based body (left column), a body with a straight cavity (central column) and a body with an optimized cavity (right column) at $Re = 2000$ and $a = 1$. Contours of vorticity range $\omega_z \in [-8, 8]$.

182 of vorticity contours for the three geometries at $a = 0.08$. Unlike the previous case of $a = 1$, for which the body's
 183 accelerating time scale is much shorter than the corresponding flow impulsive response time, the lower value of a
 184 induces weaker vortical structures, while the transitions between different phases take longer times (note that, for
 185 the case at hand, the steady body's motion is reached at $t = 12.5$). The occurrence of slower, less intense processes,
 186 involves the balance between phases duration for the different geometries. For instance, *phase A* remains present for
 187 $t \leq 8$, while for $t \geq 12$ *phase C* has already begun for all bodies. In this case, the primary vortices are smaller and
 188 less intense than those forming for $a = 1$, and do not completely penetrate inside the cavity, being easily convected
 189 downstream as the flow evolves. Therefore, any impulse associated to that particular flow dynamics is expected to
 190 have a smaller effect on the drag coefficient.

191 B. Temporal variation of near wake

192 To better identify the differences between flow dynamics concerning the three geometries under study and the role
 193 of the acceleration, we next present quantitative results of major variables characterizing the near wake, namely, the
 194 recirculation bubble length and the vortex core position i.e. temporal axial location and transversal distance. The
 195 analysis of such variables will shed some light on the performance and potential drag reduction, which will be later
 196 addressed.

Figure 4. Time sequence of spanwise vorticity ω_z of the near wake, obtained by PIV measurements, for the blunt-based body (left column), a body with a straight cavity (central column) and a body with an optimized cavity (right column) at $Re = 2000$ and $a = 0.08$. Contours of vorticity range $\omega_z \in [-8, 8]$.

198 1. Recirculation length

199 We first discuss the influence of geometry and acceleration on the recirculation length, L_{rec} , for which two different
 200 criteria have been employed (see Fig. 5a). The first method, denoted as “*axis sign*”, determines L_{rec} as the distance
 201 where the streamwise velocity at the axis $y = 0$, $u_x(x, 0, 0)$, changes from negative to positive (see dashed line in
 202 Fig. 5a). The second one, identified as “*iso contour*”, corresponds to the furthest downstream axial location of the
 203 iso-contour of zero streamwise velocity, $u_x = 0$ (see white circle on iso-contour in Fig. 5a). Notice that this point does
 204 not necessarily have to be located on the axis. Figure 5(b) shows the evolution of L_{rec} as a function of the physical
 205 traveled distance s , for the body with the optimized cavity and $a = 1$, computed by means of the two aforementioned
 206 methods. Such evolution of L_{rec} is intrinsically associated to the wake development. In the early transient, which
 207 is characterized by the symmetric wake evolution (*phase A*), trends are nearly identical for the two methods, and
 208 L_{rec} presents a monotonic increase which extends further than the accelerating time in this case (notice that, for
 209 this case, the accelerated body motion stops at $t = 1$ or, similarly, $s = 1/2 at^2 = 0.5$). This behavior represents the
 210 longer impulsive flow response to the short accelerating motion of the body. At $s \simeq 2.5$, there is a sudden change in
 211 L_{rec} defined by the “*axis sign*” method, related to the beginning of *phase B*, where the wake symmetry is broken,
 212 as corroborated by the vorticity contours in Fig. 3. In particular, once the symmetry is broken, the recirculation
 213 bubble borders are shifted transversally, away from the axis. Consequently, its furthest downstream location does not

Figure 5. (a) Methods to quantify the recirculation length, L_{rec} : “axis sign” - streamwise velocity distribution at the axis $y = 0$, $u_x(x, 0, 0)$ (dashed line); “iso contour” - furthest downstream axial location of iso-contour of nil streamwise velocity, $u_x = 0$ (white circle on solid iso-contour superimposed on the streamlines) for the straight cavity and $a = 0.5$. (b) Evolution of L_{rec} with the physical traveled distance, s , for the optimized cavity and $a = 1$, using the two identification methods for L_{rec} . Transient phases thresholds have been included for the sake of discussion.

coincide with that generated by the intersection of such region with the x -axis, and the two methods described to determine L_{rec} differ, allowing the identification of the *phase B* threshold. The transition between phases has been highlighted in Fig. 5(b) using dashed lines. After the symmetry breaking and the subsequent recirculation bubble tilting, the interaction between shear layers provokes the detachment of the first vortex downstream, thus giving rise to an effective shortening of the instantaneous recirculation region, i.e. L_{rec} decreases, which marks the beginning of *phase C*. At this new stage, oscillations of L_{rec} begin as a consequence of the transient shedding, accompanied by an overall growth of the recirculation region, which stems from the aforementioned primary eddies dissipation close to the base, and the associated pressure increase. From this point on, the recirculation region continues evolving, characterized by the growth of an irrotational region near the body base and the alternate shedding of vortices, eventually reaching the L_{rec} permanent value¹⁶.

The influence of the geometry and the acceleration value, a , on the recirculation length, L_{rec} , determined by the “iso contour” criterion, is summarized in Fig. 6 at the very early transient stages. As it has been previously mentioned, for low acceleration values, i.e. $a = 0.08$ (see Fig. 6a), the transient evolution is slower and the range of s plotted corresponds to *phase A* and *phase B*, where there are no major differences between the three geometries, although the body without cavity presents a slightly larger instantaneous L_{rec} . In fact, according to Fig. 4, symmetry breaking has already occurred around $t \simeq 12$, i.e. $s \simeq 5.76$, for all cases. At larger acceleration rates, $a = 1$ (Fig. 6b), the role of the optimized cavity becomes more evident. Thus, the inwards velocity component induced by the curved blades, promotes an earlier transition from symmetric to asymmetric wake (*phase B*), and the subsequent vortex shedding (*phase C*). However, the evolutions of L_{rec} are similar for the blunt-based body and the body with a straight cavity. The effect of the acceleration value, a , is further investigated for the optimized cavity and the blunt base in Figs. 6(c-d). In both cases, the evolution of L_{rec} almost coincides during *phase A*. However, as expected, the threshold of symmetry breaking occurs sooner at larger values of a , as the earlier local drop of L_{rec} indicates. This effect is more acute for the optimized cavity, as the comparison between Figs. 6(c) and (d) suggests.

2. Vortex Dynamics

We next discuss the evolution with the traveled physical distance, s , of the primary eddies and vortices shed as the transient process evolves. To analyze the primary eddies displacement, we will compute the maximum and minimum values of spanwise vorticity, $\max(\omega_z)$ and $\min(\omega_z)$ in the near wake. The latter variables will define the axial location of eddies cores of positive and negative vorticity, as $x_{e,+} = x(\omega_z = \max(\omega_z))$ and $x_{e,-} = x(\omega_z = \min(\omega_z))$ respectively, as well as the corresponding transversal spacing, $D_e = |y(\omega_z = \max(\omega_z)) - y(\omega_z = \min(\omega_z))|$. A graphical representation of such variables is included in Fig. 7(a), where points of maximum and minimum vorticity ω_z have been depicted. As it can be observed, these points detect the cores of eddies in the recirculation bubble for the early stages, and their tracking may allow us to identify the incipient transition to an asymmetric wake (*phase B*). Once the eddies are mitigated, this measurement will be no longer meaningful. In addition, in order to track the shed vortices during the whole time history, two new variables will be computed, namely, the axial position of the shed vortices, x_v , and their transversal distance with respect to the x -axis, y_v . To that aim, we use the method

Figure 6. Evolution of the recirculation length L_{rec} versus physical traveled distance s for different geometries (top row) at (a) $a = 0.08$ and (b) $a = 1$; and different acceleration values (bottom row) for (c) the optimized cavity and (d) the body without cavity. Here L_{rec} has been computed using the described “iso contour” method.

Figure 7. Identification of primary eddies cores and shed vortices front for the optimized cavity and $a = 0.5$, when $s = 2$: (a) axial location, $x_{e,+}$ and $x_{e,-}$, and transversal distance, D_e , obtained using the spanwise vorticity criterion; and (b) location of shed vortices, (x_{v+}, y_{v+}) and (x_{v-}, y_{v-}) , obtained by means of integral magnitudes defined in Eqs. (4) and (5). (c-f) Computation of integral magnitudes and identification of maxima and minima (dashed lines) to provide with values of x_v and y_v in (b). Contours of vorticity range $\omega_z \in [-8, 8]$.

249 proposed by Pawlak *et al.*³⁰, which is based on integral functions proportional to flux of momentum, transversal
 250 velocity changes or mass variations, throughout a defined planar region. Thus, different criteria were presented by
 251 Pawlak *et al.*³⁰ to identify the axial and transversal location of a leading vortex in a starting jet. In particular, to
 252 determine x_v , we will choose the maximum of:

Figure 8. Evolution of primary eddies with the physical traveled distance s : axial location x_e (a,c) and transversal distance between cores D_e (b,d), for the optimized cavity at $a = 0.08$ and 1 (top row); and for the three geometries under study at $a = 1$ (bottom row). Grey lines in (a,c) represent negative vorticity eddies, $x_{e,-}$, whereas black lines stand for positive ones, $x_{e,+}$.

$$I(x, t) = \int_{y_{min}}^{y_{max}} u_x^2(x, y, t) dy, \quad (4)$$

where the integration limits lie between $y_{min} = 0$ and $y_{max} = 1$, for the negative vorticity region (denoted as “- Vortex”) and $y_{min} = -1$ and $y_{max} = 0$, for the positive vorticity region (denoted as “+ Vortex”). Once the axial locations for both positive and negative vortices are computed, i.e. x_{v+} and x_{v-} , the transversal location, y_v , is computed according to,

$$I_t(y, t) = \int_{x_v}^{x_v+L_i} u_y dx, \quad (5)$$

where $L_i = 0.4$ is the axial range of integration employed in the present work. These integral variables are computed for $a = 0.5$ and the optimized cavity for $t = 3$ (or $s = 2$), and presented in Figs. 7(c-f). The results corroborate the robustness of the integral quantities, since they provide with maximum to identify x_v and y_v , as the dashed thin lines in Figs. 7(c-f) show. Note that, we have denoted the position of the primary eddies obtained from the maximum and minimum values of spanwise vorticity as $x_{e,+}$ and $x_{e,-}$ respectively. However, (x_{v+}, y_{v+}) and (x_{v-}, y_{v-}) have been used to denote the vortex position given by the integral methods (4)-(5).

The values of axial locations x_e and x_v will initially match until the primary eddies move towards the base, whereas the recirculation region continues developing evolving downstream of the body. At this point, the integral criteria will better track the leading vortex front.

Figure 8 depicts evolution of axial location of positive and negative vorticity primary eddies, $x_{e,+}$ and $x_{e,-}$, and vertical distance between them, D_e , versus s . More precisely, Fig. 8(a) shows the axial location of the upper and lower eddies emitted from the optimized cavity for the maximum and the minimum acceleration values, $a = 0.08$ and 1 respectively, whereas Fig. 8(b) depicts the corresponding transversal distance D_e for all accelerations. Thus, for small s ($s \approx 2.5$ for $a = 0.08$ and $s \approx 3.5$ for $a = 1$) the flow symmetry becomes evident, as inferred by the nearly identical evolutions of x_e corresponding to the upper and the lower vortices. In the same line, after this early period, curves start to diverge, indicating the beginning of the asymmetric phase. Moreover, the circulation of the vortices emitted increases with a , what makes them roll up faster and move towards the cavity more rapidly for $a = 1$ than for $a = 0.08$, as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Besides, D_e decreases quickly with s in both cases, caused by the geometrical configuration of the optimized cavity which induces an inwards transversal component in the flow. Moreover, a quasi asymptotic value of D_e is reached, which is related to the size of the cavity hollow. In fact, this value is attained for shorter traveled distance at low values of a . Notice that for $a = 1$, D_e is no longer meaningful for $s \simeq 6$ since an unsteady flow has already started and primary eddies do not coexist anymore inside the cavity. Figures 8 (c) and (d) show a comparison of the previous variables from the three geometries used and $a = 1$. First, the evolutions of x_e obtained with the bodies with the straight and the optimized cavities are very similar since the cavity induces a

Figure 9. Evolution of the axial location of negative front vortices, $x_{v,-}$, with the physical traveled distance, s : (a) dependence of x_v on the acceleration value a for the optimized cavity; and (b) dependence of x_v on the geometry for $a = 1$.

reverse flow that makes the eddies penetrate inside it. Conversely, in the case of the blunt-based body, eddies are allowed to grow and extend without transversal limitation, what precludes them from further approaching the base, and facilitates their downstream convection. This distinct behavior will translate into qualitatively different forces distribution, as it will be later discussed in Sect. IV. Besides, the use of cavities makes the symmetry-breaking occur earlier than in the case of bodies without cavities, where the trends of positive and negative vorticity eddies nearly overlap for the whole range of s plotted, what is in line with the observations displayed in Fig. 3. Moreover, the difference between the axial positions of the vortices is greater for the optimized cavity than for the straight one, indicating a larger asymmetry of the flow. Finally, the evolutions of transversal distance D_e displayed in Fig. 8(d) show a initial decrease with s for the three geometries. However, the value of D_e undergoes a subsequent, slight growth in the wake behind the blunt base body because, in this case, the vortices can grow without any constraint. In addition, the role of the optimized cavity seems to be associated to a regularization and more intricate interaction of eddies, as inferred from the smoother trend and lower values of D_e .

Now, we focus on the evolution of front vortices with s , obtained by the integral methods described by Eq. 4, for different geometries and acceleration values. In particular, in Fig. 9(a), we show the evolution of $x_{v,-}(s)$ for the optimized cavity and $a = 0.08$ and 1, whereas the comparison of $x_{v,-}(s)$ for different geometries at $a = 1$ is included in Fig. 9(b). Values of $x_{v,+}(s)$ are not shown for the sake of clarity, since they feature trends that are similar to those of $x_{v,-}(s)$. The first curves of each plot represent the incipient formation of the recirculation region, which is characterized by a slight growth of x_v , followed by the detachment and convection of the first vortex at the end of each trend, associated to the sudden decrease in x_v . This gap is related to the identification of a new vortex with a stronger circulation that starts to form close to the base, and end up being shed again, with the consequent increase of x_v and later sharp fall off. These discrete patterns characterize the vortex shedding process in the transient flow. The latter transient character becomes evident by the fact that both, the shedding frequency and the minimum value of x_v in each event, evolve towards the characteristic asymptotic values of the permanent regime. Regarding the role of the acceleration (see Fig. 9a), it seems clear that a larger value of a , leads to a shortening in vortex formation and occurrence of alternate shedding (or *phase C*). After the first shedding event, similar behaviors of x_v , in terms of frequencies, are observed for different values of a , as the transient flow approaches the permanent regime. On the other hand, with regard to the geometry (Fig. 9b), it becomes apparent that the optimized cavity promotes an earlier beginning of vortex shedding than in other cases, along with a more regularized pattern of x_v . These features may entail a beneficial impact on the forces distribution and the body stability, which will be next discussed.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS: ANALYSIS ON HYDRODYNAMIC FORCES

The previous experimental work was devoted to the characterization of the early transient stages, evaluating the influence of both, the geometry and acceleration values on the near wake development and topology. In view of the major modifications encountered for the main wake parameters, especially when the optimized cavity is implemented, i.e. earlier promotion of transient shedding, shortening of the recirculation and vortex formation lengths, as well as the distance between primary eddies, among others; it is relevant to evaluate the impact of such curved, optimized geometry on the forces acting on the body. Hence, to extend the previous results beyond the early transient stages,

31 here we make use of numerical simulations, which provide with exhaustive information on the flow dynamics for
 318 larger times, until the permanent shedding regime is set. Therefore, we will first validate the numerical procedure by
 319 means of comparisons with experimental results, to subsequently analyze the time evolution of forces, with particular
 320 emphasis on the potential drag reduction and weakening of oscillations amplitude that the optimized cavity may
 321 provide with.

322 A. Validation of numerical model

323 We now validate the numerical procedures by comparing the experiments and numerical results in terms of major
 324 variables, characterizing the near wake topology and vortex dynamics. Two parameters have been assessed, namely,
 325 the vortex strength, by means of the circulation, Γ , and the near wake extension characterized using the recirculation
 326 length, L_{rec} . While both the numerical and experimental evolutions of the recirculation length have been calculated
 327 using the aforementioned method “*iso contour*” (see Sect. III B), the circulation of the eddies in the early stages has
 328 been computed as

$$\Gamma = \iint_A \omega_z(x, y) dy dx \simeq [\Sigma_i \Sigma_j \omega_{z,ij} \Delta x \Delta y]_A, \quad (6)$$

329 defining A as the region comprising the eddy being tracked, where the spanwise vorticity distribution $\omega_z(x, y)$ is
 330 integrated. The analysis of vortex circulation in the first impulsive flow stages, namely *phase A* and *phase B*, will
 331 allow the characterization of the shear layer roll-up and the vortex formation, which govern the flow evolution in the
 332 transient. In that sense, Fig. 10(a) depicts the numerical and experimental evolutions of the vortex circulation, Γ ,
 333 with the physical travelled distance, s , for the straight cavity and $a = 0.5$. As it can be observed, until $s \simeq 6$ (which
 334 corresponds to $t = 7$) both trends nearly overlap, what indicates the capability of numerical simulations to accurately
 335 reproduce the evolution of eddies during the wake impulsive dynamics. In particular, as it was commented before,
 336 when the body starts to move, an incipient eddy forms due to the roll-up of the shear layer. The vortex extends
 337 spatially, increasing its circulation monotonically as vorticity is fed from the shear layer. Eventually, a maximum
 338 is reached before the vortex detaches and is expelled from the shear layer, from which we stop the computation
 339 of circulation as the vortex is convected downstream. Furthermore, a slight variation in the value of Γ between
 340 trends is observed at the very end of the analyzed process, which corresponds to the beginning of the characteristic
 341 alternate shedding process of *phase C* in the experimental results. This difference may stem from the fact that the
 342 experimental flow is subjected to small mechanical perturbations (e.g. towing system vibrations, subtle misalignments,
 343 initial movement of seeding particles) which provokes an earlier transition to unsteadiness through their convective
 344 amplification downstream from the base. However, the good agreement between the experiments and the numerics
 345 is corroborated by the evaluation of snapshots of spanwise vorticity ω_z (see Figs. 10c-f), for selected instants marked
 346 in Figs. 10(a,b), in which quite similar topologies can be observed. In particular, flows are nearly identical for early
 347 stages, until $s \simeq 5$, although the experimental wake shows already a slight asymmetry, as it can be observed in
 348 Fig. 10(e). The discrepancies previously commented, become more evident in Fig. 10(f), at $s = 6.5$ where, the noisier
 349 experimental flow exhibits a vortex already shed, which is not yet observable in the numerical results. However, the
 350 qualitative features of the near wake are still quite similar.

351 The latter phenomenon is also observed when the evolutions of the recirculation lengths, $L_{rec}(s)$, are compared, as
 352 in Fig. 10(b). This measurement gives a hint on the near wake extension. Again, the agreement between numerical
 353 and experimental trends is fairly good for $s \leq 7$, from which the experiments show an oscillating behavior, as already
 354 mentioned above. Conversely, the numerical flow presents a more stable behavior, until $s \simeq 12$. It is worth highlighting
 355 that, despite of the different initial conditions associated to the background disturbances which provides with noisier
 356 measurements from experiments, both results show similar values and evolutions with s . In view of these results,
 357 the validity of numerical simulations can be considered satisfactory, and consequently we next proceed to extend the
 358 analysis towards later stages of the transient to assess the possible benefits of the use of the optimized cavity in terms
 359 of drag coefficient and body dynamics stability.

360 B. Forces evolution

361 We first analyze the transient evolution of the drag coefficient, $C_d = F_x / (0.5 \rho u_\infty^2 WH)$, where F_x is the measured
 362 force on the x -axis, for the optimized cavity and $a = 0.5$, which is plotted in Fig. 11. This figure also includes selected
 363 snapshots with contours of spanwise vorticity, ω_z , and pressure coefficient, $C_p = (p_i - p_\infty) / (0.5 \rho u_\infty^2)$, where p_i is the
 364 local static pressure and p_∞ the reference one. Additionally, Fig. 11(a) displays the evolution of the base pressure
 365 coefficient, C_{p_b} , which has been computed by averaging the local pressure values p_i obtained for 100 points belonging

Figure 10. Comparison between numerical and experimental results: (a) vortex circulation and (b) recirculation length. Snapshots of spanwise vorticity, ω_z , (c-f) for selected distances identified in (a,b) obtained experimentally (upper row) and numerically (lower row). Contours of vorticity range $\omega_z \in [-16, 16]$.

366 to a staggered grid placed at the body base $(x, y, z) = (0, \pm 0.5, \pm 2)$. The comparison of C_d and C_{pb} will enlighten
 367 the discussion on the strong link between the near wake dynamics, previously described, and force coefficients. Thus,
 368 the evolution of the drag coefficient presents an initial peak at very early times, which corresponds to an added-mass
 369 effect stemming from the fluid acceleration caused by the body impulsive motion. Once the steady body velocity is
 370 reached at $s = 0.5$, a sudden decrease is observed for C_d , related to the flow suction and deceleration at the base,
 371 creating a stagnation region of high pressure (see snapshots in Fig. 11c). Simultaneously, the two primary eddies grow
 372 and approach the cavity. Next, for the acceleration at hand, the primary eddy detaches from the shear layer and
 373 gets inside the cavity, inducing a decrease of the base pressure (see C_p distribution and snapshots of Fig. 11d) and
 374 a subsequent increase in C_d . This event gives rise to a second local maximum in the drag at $s \approx 10$. This primary
 375 eddy interacts with the following one generated by the roll up of the shear layer, being engulfed and ejected from the
 376 cavity (panels d and e), which increases the base pressure and decreases the drag, as shown at $s \approx 16$ in Fig. 11(a) and
 377 Fig. 11(e). Finally, the eddy is tore apart, getting closer to the cavity, what decreases the base pressure and leads to
 378 the local maximum at $s \approx 21$ in the evolution of C_d . Thus, this new maximum corresponds to the shedding of a vortex
 379 that separates from the shear layer, which has been identified previously as the beginning of *phase C* (see snapshots
 380 in Figs. 11e-f). A similar dynamics and forces distributions have been reported by Fernando and Rival²⁶, in the
 381 case of elliptical and rectangular accelerating plates of different aspect ratios. Afterwards, a more chaotic, oscillating
 382 behavior is observed from $s \geq 30$ to $s \leq 50$, in which C_d increases. The initial steep growth is correlated with a
 383 shortening of the vortices formation length with time, together with the vortex shedding (note that the recirculation
 384 region in panel e is larger than that in panel g). In this interval of time, vortex shedding goes through a transient
 385 period, modulating the amplitude of the C_d and C_{pb} oscillations, until it reaches a periodic permanent behavior at
 386 $s > 50$, characterized by the natural oscillations frequency and time-averaged value of drag, i.e. $St_w = f_v h / u_\infty = 0.22$
 387 and $\bar{C}_d \approx 0.61$. The aforementioned drag evolution strongly correlates with the C_{pb} evolution displayed in Fig. 11(a),
 388 showing a nearly opposite correspondence. Therefore, it seems evident that, for the value of Re at hand, the main
 389 contribution to drag reduction is the form drag, guided by the pressure field around the body.

390 The effect of geometry and acceleration value is analyzed in Fig. 12, where distributions of drag coefficient for the
 391 three bodies under study, are included, for $a = 0.08$ (Fig. 12a) and $a = 1$ (Fig. 12b). At first sight, it becomes evident
 392 that the added-mass peak for low values of a is smaller, as a consequence of the lower inertial effect. In all cases, C_d
 393 rapidly decreases after the accelerated motion stops, as previously commented. However, note that, such decrease is
 394 steeper for the bodies with cavities, that undergo a monotonic increase of C_d after a while. In that sense, two different
 395 behaviors have been identified concerning this drag valley prior to the monotonic increase, which are strongly linked
 396 to the effect of acceleration and geometry. Thus, for low acceleration values, i.e. $a = 0.08$, this transition occurs

Figure 11. (a) Drag and base pressure coefficient evolutions with physical traveled distance, $C_d(s)$ (solid line) and $C_{pb}(s)$ (dashed line), for the optimized cavity and $a = 0.5$. (b-g) Snapshots with contours of pressure coefficient (top row) and spanwise vorticity (bottom row) corresponding to selected values of s identified in (a). Note that $C_{pb}(s)$ is obtained by averaging pressure values taken at 100 points belonging to a staggered grid placed at the base region $(x, y, z) = (0, \pm 0.5, \pm 2)$.

smoothly, whereas for large acceleration values, i.e. $a = 0.5$ and 1 , local maxima are identified (see Figs. 11 and 12b), which, as commented earlier, emerge from the effect of primary eddies and shed vortices in the drag coefficient. Actually, the lack of such secondary peaks for the low accelerated motion is due to the fact that, in this case, the vortex circulation is not sufficiently large to make them go towards the cavity and they are convected downstream by the mean flow (see values of ω_z for comparison in Figs. 3 and 4). Conversely, the body without cavity shows a nearly constant value of minimum drag for a longer period, which is related to a longer residence time of the primary eddies close to the base. This slower dynamics turns into a later transition to the alternate oscillating shedding period, where the drag attains significantly large oscillating values, as it can be seen for $s > 60$ in Figs. 12(a,b). Moreover, the beginning of this oscillating behavior for the drag takes place earlier for the bodies with a cavity. However, both the oscillations amplitude and the maximum value of C_d reached are smaller for the body with the optimized cavity than for the other two geometries, thus providing with a relevant potential drag reduction at the late stages of the transient ($s > 40$ for $a = 0.08$ and $s > 25$ for $a = 1$). This effect becomes more evident for larger values of a , where the transition to the permanent, asymptotic regime occurs much faster and even without any oscillating in the case of the body with the optimized cavity.

In order to quantify the benefits of the optimized cavity provided by the more rapid transition toward the permanent regime in the wake, characterized additionally by a weaker oscillating behavior, we will next calculate the time to reach the permanent state, as well as the averaged and integrated values of the drag coefficient over the total transient period. The latter values will be computed considering the transient spatial horizon or traveled distance until the flow reaches the permanent regime, s_p , for every geometry at each acceleration value. Furthermore, the integrated value of the drag coefficient is related to the energy needed to overcome the drag. The value s_p will be defined as the traveled distance fulfilling the following two conditions: first, the averaged drag value within a window of extension $\Delta s = 10$, must reach the permanent averaged drag value, with a difference of $\pm 5\%$; and second, the drag coefficient standard deviation must be below 1% of the permanent value of C_d . Now, the accumulated total transient drag or dimensionless consumed energy to overcome the drag, E_{C_d} , is defined as,

Figure 12. Comparison of drag coefficient evolutions with physical traveled distance, $C_d(s)$, for the optimized cavity (solid line), straight cavity (dashed line) and blunt-based body (dotted line), for (a) $a = 0.08$ and (b) $a = 1$.

	Geometry	s_p	\bar{C}_d	E_{C_d}	$R(\%)$
$a = 0.08$	WOC	230	0.731	168.9	-
	STR	107	0.612	65.4	61.3
	OPT	65	0.450	29.3	82.6
$a = 1$	WOC	210	0.740	155.4	-
	STR	80	0.642	51.4	66.9
	OPT	50	0.448	22.4	85.5

Table I. Transient regime drag reduction: physical traveled distance needed to reach the permanent regime, s_p , averaged drag coefficient, \bar{C}_d , accumulated drag coefficient, E_{C_d} , and drag reduction relative to the body without cavity, $R(\%) = (\bar{C}_d - \bar{C}_{d,WOC})/\bar{C}_{d,WOC}$. Time-averaged values of drag coefficients computed by Lorite-Díez *et al.*¹⁶ in the permanent regime are respectively: $\bar{C}_{d,WOC} = 0.819$, $\bar{C}_{d,STR} = 0.778$ and $\bar{C}_{d,OPT} = 0.609$.

$$E_{C_d} = \int_0^{s_p} C_d(s) ds. \quad (7)$$

Table I lists the values of the physical traveled distance needed to reach the permanent regime, s_p , together with the corresponding consumed energy and averaged drag, E_{C_d} and \bar{C}_d , for the three geometries and accelerations $a = 0.08$ and $a = 1$. The reduction of drag coefficient within the transient, with respect to the body without cavity is also included, $R(\%) = (\bar{C}_d - \bar{C}_{d,WOC})/\bar{C}_{d,WOC}$. As previously commented, in order to evaluate the real energy expense during transient period and its reduction, we choose as integration limit for each geometry their own value of s_p .

Moreover, the values of s_p corroborate the faster transition to permanent regime induced by the use of the optimized cavity. Besides, the values of averaged drag and consumed energy clearly show the significant improvement provided by the optimized cavity, compared to both the blunt-based body and the one with the straight cavity. Quantitatively, the optimized geometry leads to a transient drag reduction $R(\%)$ of nearly 82.6% for $a = 0.08$ and 85.5% for $a = 1$ when compared to the blunt base, which correspond to respective reductions of 55.2% and 56.4% with respect to the straight cavity, thus extending to impulsively motions the better performance of the optimized geometry previously reported for permanent regimes¹⁶. Such reduction, translates into a significantly lower energy needed, E_{C_d} , and consequently an expected smaller transient aerodynamic load. In view of such results, this configuration can be potentially considered as an efficient passive device to reduce the effect of aerodynamics forces on the body, as well as to improve the body motion stability. The results reported in this work are expected to apply for more realistic flow conditions, as already corroborated by Lorite-Díez *et al.*¹⁶, who observed that, in the permanent regime, the drag reduction obtained when an optimized cavity is implemented at the base of the body increases with the Reynolds number.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented experimental and numerical studies on the flow induced by an impulsive motion of a simplified bluff body from rest, under different values of acceleration and three distinct rear geometrical configurations, inspired on wake passive control devices. The main goal of the present study is to assess the performance of such topologies in transient flow conditions, which are very common in real transport applications and usually not evaluated in classical

studies on wake control. Thus, in view of the complexity that wakes behind three-dimensional bluff bodies imply, and to better identify the physical mechanisms governing the dynamics and instability of such flows, we have analyzed the impulsive motion of a D-shaped body implementing a blunt base, a straight cavity and a curved cavity, for four different values of dimensionless acceleration, i.e. $a = 0.08, 0.2, 0.5$ and 1 , starting from rest and reaching a permanent regime of $Re = 2000$. Special focus has been paid on the latter geometry, which constitutes a new control wake device design, whose shape is obtained through adjoint-based optimization algorithms, thus providing with a large reduction of the drag coefficient and a more regularized and less chaotic wake in permanent flow regimes¹⁶. Therefore, the impact on the near wake evolution and forces distributions has been considered, which is strongly linked to body's motion stability and more importantly, their aerodynamic loads.

First, an experimental characterization of the near wake development has been performed in a towing tank, using PIV measurements. Contours of spanwise vorticity have been analyzed to identify the different phases characterizing the transient flow evolution and variations of wake features during such flow development. A first stage, denoted as *phase A*, is observed during the early period, in which symmetric shear layers roll up into two primary eddies, configuring a symmetry wake. As a consequence of the flow suction caused by the impulsive motion at the base, primary eddies are attracted towards the rear part of the body, while they continue growing, as observed in Figs. 2 and 4. This initial phase is characterized by the monotonous growth of the recirculation length, L_{rec} , and the eddies circulation Γ (see Figs. 5 and 10, respectively). Eventually, the interaction between shear layer provokes the destabilization of the flow and the wake symmetry is broken, what represents the beginning of a new period, denoted *phase B*. The identification of such transition is related to a local decrease of the recirculation length value L_{rec} , along with a deviation on the evolution of the axial location of primary eddies, x_e (Fig. 8). After a short interval, the flow instability settles down and an alternate transitional shedding of front vortices begins, giving rise to the so-called *phase C*, that features large variations on the recirculation length value. The alternate shedding is further investigated by means of the tracking of axial position of front vortices, x_v , which is identified employing integral methods, as defined in Eqs. (4)-(5)³⁰. Such process has been noted to be a developing stage in which both the formation length and the vortex detachment location evolve with time (see Fig. 9), at the end of which the permanent flow regime is expected to be retrieved, as it has been later shown by means of numerical simulations. Furthermore, different transient behaviors have been observed in terms of acceleration values and geometry. More precisely, larger values of a have been proven to foster the earlier transition between described phases. This effect becomes more evident when the axial location of front vortices, x_v , is evaluated (see Fig. 9). Additionally, a higher acceleration is related to a stronger suction of primary eddies, which move closer to the base (Fig. 8a), presenting larger values of vorticity which allow them to reside longer periods by the base (Figs. 3 and 4). With regard to the role of geometry, the use of cavities has been shown to limit the growth of the primary eddies, due to the influence of the hollow size, which contributes to a speeding-up of the transitions between phases. As far as the new optimized, curved cavity is concerned, it has been shown to have a significant impact on the near wake features when compared to the remaining geometries. In summary, the optimized configuration leads to a shortening of both the recirculation length and the formation length, while producing a shorter transition between phases (see e.g. Figs. 3 and 6), along with a more regularized, less chaotic alternate shedding, as the neat trends in the distributions of x_v displays (Fig. 9b).

Next, in order to explore the beneficial effects regarding drag reduction and amplitude of forces oscillations that the aforementioned wake modifications induced by the optimized cavity, we have performed direct numerical simulations, that have allowed to extend the previous results to longer temporal horizons. Thus, a validation analysis has been first conducted to ensure the accuracy and appropriateness of the numerical results. To that aim, selected flow variables, such as eddies circulation and recirculation length, along with snapshots of spanwise vorticity (Fig. 10), have been compared. A remarkable agreement between experiments and simulations has been found for the early stages, where values and trends match, whereas slight differences have been detected only for longer times (note that an earlier triggering of alternate shedding in the experiments takes place as a consequence of the larger level of background noise, e.g. mechanical vibrations).

A subsequent analysis of drag coefficient has allowed to relate near wake dynamics and forces values (Fig. 11), corroborating the previous hypothesis on the potential positive effect of the use of optimized cavity. The latter becomes clear when the drag C_d is compared for the three geometries at hand (Fig. 12). In general, the aforementioned smoother and faster transition gives rise to a general smaller averaged value of drag together with less energetic instantaneous fluctuations of C_d , regardless the acceleration value. Finally, a quantification of such potential drag reduction and shortening of the transient regime has been computed, as shown in Table I. In particular, the limit of the developing wake has been characterized by means of the variable, s_p , which represents the traveled distance until the flow reaches the permanent regime.

Thus, the value of s_p corresponding the optimized cavity is, for the case at hand, one fourth of that from the body without cavity, and always considerably lower than that associated to the classical straight cavity. Furthermore, in all cases, an important drag reduction in terms of averaged values, \bar{C}_d , or consumed energy, E_{C_d} , has been obtained for the optimized cavity, which attains almost a 55% reduction for both acceleration values evaluated, when compared

to the straight cavity (and nearly 85% regarding the blunt-based body).

In summary, the optimized cavity configuration has demonstrated to be an appealing and efficient passive device which shows a great potential to reduce both the drag coefficient averaged value and instantaneous drag oscillations for impulsively flow regimes. The features may help improving the body motion stability, and could be used in practical transport applications. These observations extend the corresponding beneficial effect already reported for permanent regimes¹⁶, and highlight the relevance of the use of optimization algorithms applied to flow control.

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